

THE DEATH OF GWEN STACY AND ITS IMPACT ON THE COMIC WORLD

 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7811274

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ABSTRACT

This essay-article addresses the topic of how the death of Gwen Stacy, the girlfriend of Peter Parker, Spider-Man, impacted comics after the event. The relevance of this study lies in discussing the impact of fictional characters on real life and how they become part of human existence, becoming important and, later, when they leave these scenarios, the void they leave, accompanied by I miss you immensely. Gwen Stacy was a very important character in the stories of the *Web Head*, helping him to find himself in the midst of the turmoil of disconnected thoughts arising from a multifaceted existence with countless responsibilities, which generated a crisis of anguish and melancholy, unparalleled. Peter tries to remember her as an innocent and, at the same time, mature girl; full of life and joy. The impact of her death was so devastating that, after it happened, whenever Peter Parker looked in the mirror, he could no longer see a Super Hero; he always saw someone who had failed [*who he loved the most*] and what's more, all superheroes came to see themselves as failureable individuals. Much worse than this, society, ordinary individuals, finally understood that they were not the infallible gods in which all their faith was placed. A good part of Blondie or Buddy from the Neighborhood fans have not forgiven the writers for what they did, not to Gwen Stacy or the pain they inflicted on Parker, but for what they did to them. She deserves the place of honor that she holds in the memory of fans and, it can be said that over the next fifty years, several other works tend to emerge, enhancing her memory and her charming glow that, for years, guided Spider-Man through the dark path of being a teenage Super-Hero, with a load of enemies that would make any other of the genre, already established in the Comics World, envious.

Keywords: Gwendolyne Maxime Stacy. Peter parker. World of Comics. Spiderman. The death of Gwen Stacy.

INTRODUCTION

Gwendolyne Stacy, the charming young blonde who left the world of comics so early, is an unsolved enigma. The character was created by Stan Lee and Steve Ditko, first appearing in *The Amazing Spider-Man* #31 (December 1965 issue). It had a period of passage through the world of comics of less than 8 years, but that proved to be enough for all the stories of Super-Heroes [both *Marvel Comics* and *DC Comics*] from then on to be rethought and an unbeatable opponent was inserted in this particular universe: *tragic guilt* . Along with it came indecision as to whether or not everything they were doing was worthy of merit. Strange that, when you analyze in depth, the feeling of each Super-Hero closed in their particular being, what you notice is that there was a very deep isolation of each one of them, closing themselves in their own worlds. They distanced themselves from society.

Gwen Stacy ends up killed by the Green Goblin in *The Amazing Spider-Man* #121 (June 1973 issue). His death is such a controversial chapter in comic book history that, arguably, it represents an unhealed wound. Stan Lee (1922-2018) always gave unclear answers about the decision to end the young woman's participation in the Spider-Man stories. It's not about death itself; but, the way it all happened and how it ends: a paradox in which the always late Parker was there, precisely at that moment. Different from the usual conceptual model in which the Hero is not able to arrive in time to save the victim, this time he was there, fighting and everything happens in the middle of the clash and what was supposed to be one more adventure turns into misadventure, nightmare and guilt .

Peter was a shy boy who kept a terrible secret, a double identity in which the secret always put him in action, motivated by the words of his Uncle Ben, who could not interpret and, driven by duty and responsibility, he acted like a gifted teenager. of superhuman abilities. What he didn't realize is that his actions left a trail of destruction and death that would one day lead him to reflect on his responsibility as a superhero.

Gwen never cared about Peter's frequent and constant delays, which, along with this, was always broke, trying to help his Aunt in some way, who was also having a hard time because of the loss of her husband, victim of a thief who murdered. Parker felt guilty for Tio's death, first because he had lied about where he was going to be and then because he refused to stop the robber of the ring cashier, having been deceived by the owner of the establishment.

The Enchantress Stacy never questioned him about what happened to the young man's parents, which was a state secret, since they were accused of treason and, for this reason, given officially as dead by the state bureaucracy. Coincidentally, they were employees of Oscorp,

Norman Osborn's company, who would become the Green Goblin, after applying the Goblin Serum to himself, which he had developed under the name of Formula Goblin (Goblin Formula).

The impact of his death was so vast that whenever Peter Parker looked in the mirror afterward, he could no longer see a Super Hero; I always saw someone who had failed [*who I loved the most*] and what's more, all superheroes came to see themselves as failureable individuals. Much worse than this, society, ordinary individuals, finally understood that they were not the infallible gods in which all their faith was placed.

A sentence from the Joker addressed to his great Friend illustrates well the feeling they started to have after the failure of the Friend of the Neighborhood with Gwen: "The great Batman is not the hero I expected, after all!"¹

Gwen didn't die thinking this about the Great Scarlet Hero. She was certain that she would be saved by that masked stranger; after all, he was the Hero everyone expected him to be; never failed. But, on that fateful day, in which a short time before he had already failed Captain George Stacy [*Gwen's father*], nothing would surprise him more than the failure caused by his arrogance.

What haunts Peter's thoughts more: Gwen's violent death, at his hands, or his shattered vanity? Norman managed to prove to young Parker that he wasn't the Hero he believed himself to be! It showed him how human he was, all too human. Years later, in one of his crises, his Aunt May will tell him that it was this human side of him that made him a hero, a Super-Hero. Contrary to what one might try to believe, society has not come to judge them as monsters. In a strange way, they still considered them essential figures in their lives, since they had no control over how things happen in life.

It wasn't Gwen who abruptly changed the trajectory of comics. The way he leaves the scene was something completely out of the fantastic mold used for the characters in the stories. She died, literally, having her neck broken, not from the fall, but from the impact caused by the abrupt stop, when Parker tries to save her.

Who could try to resuscitate her, using all his knowledge of genetic engineering, was the one that Peter would never ask for help and, thus, the beautiful and beautiful Gwen Stacy leaves the world of comics to live in the world of memory of Peter Benjamin Parker. During his stay in the Amazing Spider-Man stories, he formed a perfect pair with the Hero.

¹BATMAN. *Ninja* . 85 minutes, 2018.

It never bothered her that Peter was always late for every appointment; always broken. In every meaningless excuse that the teenager gave her, she just smiled, because nothing was more important to her than the love she received. There was the fact that her father greatly admired that shy boy and when he discovered his secret identity, he remained discreet, never revealing it to his daughter nor opposing their relationship.

Peter was never able to understand Gwen's love for him; but it was Captain Stacy's respect that ensured this feeling to the end. When she dies, all the friends are silent and do not go to Parker to comfort him; perhaps because they realized that he was expressing a very strange kind of pain, an expression of deep feeling mixed with guilt; but, no one knew how to explain what they were seeing in the young man's eyes. It was strange that there was a feeling of revenge if the cause of the fatality was a super powerful villain that no one knew the identity of. For everyone, the question was: what could Parker have done to save his girlfriend?

Mary Jane was the only one who went to the Parker house to offer comfort to Peter, and she ends up being shooed out of there, not because the pain he was feeling at that moment was too heavy; it was the image that the redhead revealed of herself all the time that led him to believe that she was faking any regret for her friend's death. Peter saw her as someone completely alienated from the existence of others.

There was something deeper in the pain that consumed the Hero, it was his torn ego. Before, he had already failed his uncle Ben Parker; however, it was a question of cause and consequence, a fatality with which he could not directly cope with what had happened. This time it was very different, it wasn't about having failed to save the love of his life; the hand that had killed Gwen, directly, was his own; finally, he understood that he was not the hero he believed himself to be.

There was no way Peter could welcome Red into his home; how to explain to her that he was the one who had caused her death, without revealing another absurd secret. I was at a crossroads and unable to choose which way to go. He chooses a third, that of raw and brutal revenge against Norman, and ends up desolate, once again, because when he reached his goal, he did not reach the state of happiness he had hoped for. He would have to live silently with the guilt and with his own conscience punishing him.

Parker, when he hunts down and brings about the death of his Uncle Ben's murderer, felt a satisfaction and an elevation of spirit that became incomprehensible to him and he never bothered to analyze this feeling. In his heart, he held the belief that hunting and killing the Green Goblin, avenging Gwen, would make him experience the same feeling. Turns out they are two different situations; feelings of guilt provoked by very different conditions, in which

the first one was punishing the real culprit for the evil; in the second, he was trying to transfer a responsibility to someone else because of shattered pride. He realized, in time, that it wasn't Peter Parker who was wounded in his ego; it was the beast that lived within him, coursing through his veins through his DNA.

When, many years later, in his memories of Gwen, Peter says that she would like him to move on and resume his life, there are two very strong points to highlight: the first is that Blondie loved him, very much. sincere and, would always want the best for him. The second is that she died not knowing he was Spider-Man. It can be deduced that the Young Woman died grateful for that unknown Hero trying to save her. This question, in particular, changes the entire epistemological and also empirical configuration that one can rely on to interpret the death of Gwendolyne Maxime Stacy and the entire framework of feelings that surround it, directly and indirectly.

GWENDOLYNE MAXIME STACY

Gwen Stacy, as she became known to all fans of the charming Blondie, who appeared to pair with Friend from the Neighborhood in the comics published by Marvel Comics, had a quick, however, epic and legendary passage through the world of comics. Its emergence took place because the stunning redhead Mary Jane Watson was the complete opposite of the shy and quiet Peter Parker, an ideal that contrasted with his withdrawn personality.

From the beginning, the writers' interest was to unite Peter Parker and Mary Jane, creating a perfect couple along the lines of comics, which were based on Freudian psychoanalytic precepts and, also, on the conventional wisdom that opposites attract. Countless times, the redhead who was able to stop the signal went to May Parker's house looking for her nephew and, as usual, he wasn't, immersed in his superhero work.

Peter saw Mary Jane as a haughty and, paradoxically, empty girl, always trapped in her own world and making everyone around her see her as the only star in the sky. Of course, this particular way of representing her was the product of her thinking dominated by fear and withdrawn from life. Since the death of his parents, the cause of which was never revealed and the subsequent accusation of betrayal, Peter had withdrawn, sort of *a fortiori*, into a secret world, hiding ambiguous feelings towards his parents, in which he felt that they had abandoned him and, later on, his Uncle Ben also dies, which makes him sink even deeper into this misunderstood universe of his thinking, always torn between guilt and hatred towards those he loved.

Gwen was considered the most beautiful girl in the College. It was because of Parker's move to share an apartment with Harry Osborn, son of Norman Osborn, the most brilliant genetic engineer the world knew, and whose genius in the world of science was only surpassed by his total lack of ethics. As part of Harry's select group of friends, Peter ends up meeting Blonde and she ends up feeling attracted to the boy, which culminates in a teenage romance marked, on the one hand, by Parker's complete lack of commitment to his girlfriend. , always late for meetings; always apologizing and increasingly feeling guilty that Gwen always had a smile on her face and not the least bit nervous with him.

Gwendolyne Stacy was the daughter of respected NYPD Captain George Stacy. She was motherless and counting on an aunt; no one but her father, who watched over her very carefully and was quite happy that his daughter had fallen in love with a boy, even if he was the complicated teenage superhero dressed as a spider and who had achieved a respectable range. enemies, each more powerful than the last.

In a strange, incomprehensible way, she loved Peter, and maybe that was why her father kept her in the dark about her boyfriend's big secret. The boy's disappearances, the appearance of the Scarlet Champion, Parker's posture when no one was watching him... Captain Stacy knew very well that one day, his double life would end up putting his daughter at imminent risk; but for now it was worth the pleasure of seeing his lovely Gwen smiling again; expressing authentic happiness; something I hadn't seen in her since the early loss of her mother and which, given the Captain's silence regarding his daughter's consort, it can be deduced that, in some way, he carried an immense amount of guilt for what had happened.

The big question is, what had she seen in Peter that had drawn her to the point of falling in love with him? Perhaps nothing, and this simplicity was the indelible mark on both characters during the time they lived the novel. The loss of her mother may have been too much of a blow for her to bear in silence. Even if you have never touched on the subject, it is exactly this fact that marks the dimension of suffering and, sometimes, it cannot be interpreted in this way, and should be seen as a pathos , a deep, confused and dubious *feeling* in relation to the situation and in towards the object of love that is transmuted into *an object of love and hate*, because of this puerile uncertainty about the causes of death.

Gwen felt the need for true love, and Parker, even though he was a high school student, was apparently irresponsible in everyone's eyes, always arriving late for appointments; to her it made no difference; after all, his father was a mirror in which he saw himself and, being a serious man, his work was always causing him to be out and not fulfilling all his promises as

he wanted. In his mind, Peter was engaged in some secret activity that occupied most of his free time. I was completely right!

But, Gwen was a teenager and loved to think that her boyfriend was hunting or chasing bad men, because the only male figure she had as a role model was her father, a Captain of the NYPD and who took his job very seriously. If you knew you were right, one more time..., what would you feel? Quite possibly, she wouldn't abandon her love because of this and that was it, this certainty about her daughter's feelings that had made George Stacy keep secret about Parker's double life. He knew well the daughter he had raised alone since the loss of his wife. That docile and sweet face hid an incredible strength, so intense that, even after death, it still hasn't lost its beauty and charm.

Gwen and Parker were the same: two children who were lost in a world that revolved around them without understanding why everything was affecting them. Peter had only his Aunt May for family, and Blondie Lovely had only her father. There was an Aunt; but, it was only a statement; was never seen. Her father's death launches her into a spiral that would end in her marriage to Arachnid.

This may sound a little pedantic today; but, it was the 1970s and women were not ashamed to look for a strong shoulder to feel supported. Gwen was this type, a qualified student who didn't feel out of character for wanting the comfort of a home, next to the one she loved. Perhaps, for Parker, the fear of taking on a serious relationship was his poor condition, which made him feel even more depressed.

Such was Blondie's strength that she became the protagonist's girlfriend, one of the most charming romantic couples that comics have ever produced. Half a century after his death, he continues to delight Spider-Man fans as soon as they learn of his existence. The dispute between her and Mary Jane for the heart of the Head of the Web was fierce and, always with lame excuses, Peter ran away from both until he couldn't take it anymore and found himself involved.

Gwen became a kind of safe haven in the hero's tumultuous life, before so lonely and always tormented. Her simple presence represented a balm and consolation in times of distress, not forgetting that she always defended him, like when he slapped a college classmate who called Peter a coward. Parker's situation was a bit strange and paradoxical, because he disappeared and, right after that, the loudmouthed Scarlet Hero appeared, saving the day from some crazy villain who was keen to spoil everyone's well-being. But, the next day, charming and very real photos of Spider-Man in combat appeared in the newspaper *The Daily Bugle*, signed by Peter Benjamin Parker, which removed any doubt about that idiot being the Greatest Hero of New York, the Friend of the Neighborhood .

Like Peter, Gwen Stacy also showed a great evolution as a character, moving away from the spoiled and arrogant girl of her first appearances, whether it was making it clear to Flash Thompson that she would never betray Peter or telling Aunt May, even rudely, that her nephew he had already grown up and become a man. She needed to state this to justify the intention of marrying the Hero.

One detail that led to this is that Spider-Man's audience also matured, even aged and, likewise, needed more forceful stories, such as the evolution of human history itself. In this sense, by removing a great love from Parker and in such a violent way that it left an insurmountable sequel in his thought and life story, it represented the greatest move that could ever be executed in a plot. Such a move allowed the character to remain childlike for years, without public opinion complaining about such a situation.

WHY DIDN'T GWEN COME BACK TO LIFE IN THE COMICS?

In the world of literature, in particular, that was being built, in a silent way, after the emergence of Psychoanalysis, the supporting characters of the heroes are their imperfect shadows, making it clear, with such a statement that they represent the imperfections of the protagonists and that, as such, , need to be overcome, that is, the main character, the chosen one, needs to mature, leave his childish ties, be polished in such a way that he can become an adult, perfect.

Many centuries before Freud, the aedo Homer (928-898 a.n.e) created this format of purification of the hero, in his epic *Odyssey* , in which Ulysses is lost on the high seas for twenty years, losing each one of his sailors. Each one of them that succumbed meant that a negative feeling had been suppressed in favor of a rebirth and growth of himself, as a man.

In comics this is much explored, in which the Hero's companions, each with a vice that their master abhors, but supports, are lost and, much more clearly are the villains in which they express, in an open and evident way, everything that society denies. The Champion's victory over them is an expression of the Champion's inner conflict; until the point comes when the enemy is slain, demonstrating that the evil [*itself*] has been overcome.

In this way, every death in the comic book universe is symbolic. This is because the dead villain or hero can come back to life at any moment, for the simple fact that they represent non-living individuals; but, feelings and, there is a law in Physics and Psychology that is applied, *ipsis literalis* , to human existence, which is that an object, when it comes into existence, never ceases to exist, a situation presented and proven by Freud when he dealt with

the unconscious and its actions. No feeling, whether good or bad, can be destroyed or transformed; it can, at best, be sublimated, or kept secret until it finds the ideal opportunity to reveal itself once more.

Bruno Bettelheim (1903-1990) was a pioneer in the analysis of this field and, in his classic *A Psicanálise dos Contos de Fadas*, he performs a masterful interpretation of the theme, presenting details of classic works and how this entire plot is constructed, leading the reader to have a deep relationship with the subject itself, interpreting it via the unconscious. Marie-Louise Von Franz (1915-1998) also follows Bettelheim's line and clarifies other points, broadening the understanding of the relationship between the Hero and the Villain, which is a conflicting relationship with oneself ; that is, both are represented by a single being. In Brazil, Diana Corso and Mário Corso carry out an analytical work on classic works, especially fairy tales, in order to expand the semantic universe about these creatures and how editors and authors construct the plots. Sérgio Rodrigues de Souza is another author and researcher who dedicates himself exclusively to superheroes, with several works already published, highlighting, among them, the classic *A Liga da Justiça no Divã* , *As Faces Escondidas* by Kal L and two more works about Spider-Man.²

Gwen Stacy's death in the comics goes against everything that was discussed and exposed above. Generally, a participant in the hero's life dies so that he can overcome his childishness and be reborn stronger, more manly, more intellectually mature and overcome feelings of depression and anguish. With Peter, it was exactly the opposite, his loss had the interest of keeping him trapped in a condition of childlike hatred, plunging him deeper into a melancholy that crossed the entire universe of comics, putting all superheroes under suspicion, from there on.

Another striking situation is that deaths, in the world of comics, are always of a symbolic nature, ie, the condition in which the character dies leaves an open permanent doubt about what happened. If there is an explosion, or if he drowns, the body is not seen; if it is hit by shots or perforating elements, these do not hit the vital organs. Everything is planned so that the character's rebirth in future stories can seem as real as possible. At most, he spends some time disappearing from the stories until a favorable environment for his resurgence is built, where he narrates what, in fact, happened at the fateful moment and how he escaped a definitive death.

Sir Arthur Conan Doyle (1859-1930) faced a serious problem in killing his great hero Sherlock Holmes. He did it once and, given the great pressure from the public, had to resurrect

²These works and many others by the aforementioned author can be found at Editora PerSe: www.perse.com.br.

it in a new arc of stories. When he decides finally, definitively, to his Detective, he has to endure the wrath of his fans who, in fact, and to his anguish, he discovered that they were fans of his creation.

There is an affective bond that is created between the character and the readers, which is as if the first were real, someone with whom one builds bonds and a deep relationship of friendship and affection. This is the main reason why deaths, in comics and literature, in general, are symbolic. It is a form of respect for the feelings of readers and a way for the expectation of the return of the Champion or the Villain to the stories to remain active. As a literary character is not someone you live with, directly, it is impossible to miss him; what one feels is nostalgia, a nostalgia of being able to see him mirror courage and determination in the fight against evil; this when you are approaching the Super-Heroes. When referring to villains, they are usually funny, determined in their most outlandish plans and, just like readers, they love the Hero, admire and respect him; another reason why they end up being loved by the public, generating legions of fans, without this saying anything about the character of those who admire them.

In a way not explained, so far, by the editors of *The Amazing Spider-Man*, Gwen's death did not happen in a symbolic way. It was very real and from a cause that is beyond repair. To confirm the death, two agents of the New York Police confirmed the death of the Young Woman, in addition to other obscure characters who declared that they heard the crack of the neck being broken with the impact of the stop caused by the Spider's web. Gwen Stacy is definitely dead!

The comic features a *popping sound effect* next to Gwen Stacy's head in the panel where Spider-Man's web catches her. In *The Amazing Spider-Man* #125 (published October 1973), *Marvel Comics* editor Roy Thomas wrote in the letter column that "it saddens us to have to say that the bullwhip effect she suffered when Spider's web stopped her so suddenly was, in fact, what killed her. In short, it was impossible for Peter to save her. He couldn't have fallen in time; the action he took resulted in her death; if he had done nothing, she would surely have perished. There was no way out."

In an attempt to justify [*and not explain the death of Parker's girlfriend*], Gerry Conway argued that Gwen and Peter made a *perfect couple* ; but, taking that relationship to the extreme, the next level (marriage or at least Peter revealing his secret identity to her) would *betray everything Spider-Man was* , namely personal tragedy and anguish as the root of Peter's life as a Man. -Spider. Killing Gwen Stacy was a perfect opportunity to kill two birds with one

stone: to sever the relationship [*seen as*] *inadequate* and reinforce the element of personal tragedy that was, in his opinion, the essence of Spider-Man (DUEBEN, 2015).

First of all, it is necessary to try to interpret, in a hermeneutic way, the particular semantic meaning of the expression *inadequate relationship* for the two characters. It makes sense to arrive at an understanding that the author wanted to say *perfect relationship* and, as if saying this, there would be no way to explain the abrupt and wild end of something that aroused envy, for its Apollonian elegance. At no time could keeping his identity as a Super-Hero hidden from his beloved be considered as an act of betrayal, because there would always be the justification used by another great icon, Batman, that the concealment of this truth has the goal, maintaining the safety of those you love. He says this especially in relation to the use of a mask to hide the face and, consequently, personal identity.

Second, Peter Parker and Spider-Man were two antagonistic and distinct characters in terms of what they felt. Once you put on your mask and uniform, the primal animal in your DNA took complete control and everything became fantasy. The shy and quiet schoolboy turned into an inveterate loudmouth, jokester and full of pride. Loneliness was the only enemy that neither Peter nor the Neighborhood Buddy could overcome. When alone, all thoughts of anguish and melancholy took over him and this, because his body shared space with a spider, a being that is enchanted with the hunt and with the game it weaves with its victim, while this fights, in a desperate way, to try to save himself from certain death. It's the same thing he does with his opponents, irritating them to the point of collapsing and losing the fight, due to nervousness; not necessarily because they are weaker than the opponent.

In an attempt to answer the question that opens this topic: why didn't Gwen come back to life in the comics?, it presents, as an objective answer, the fact that her death was not symbolic; it was real and marked by sworn witnesses through the state. There was a clear interest in her never returning to the Spider-Man universe and its stories. Second, science still hasn't discovered a cure for a broken neck. Even if there are prostheses and other fancy things, this is a type of death that is characterized as *a fait accompli*.

THE IMPACT OF GWEN STACY'S DEATH ON THE COMIC WORLD

Many American researchers consider the Spider-Man story arc, which ends with the Death of Gwen, to be the end of the *Silver Age* and the beginning of the so-called *Bronze Age*. This era would comprise the publications launched between the 1970s and the beginning of the

1980s, extending until approximately the year 1985, in which one has the freedom to insert a greater impact of reality to the events that mark the lives of heroes. and the people around him.

According to Blumberg (2003, sp),

[Gwen Stacy's death] is the event that many cite as the most touching and most memorable event in fans' collective memory . The story, he continues to argue, would represent the apex of an ideal that several professionals had been defending in that transition period: approaching more mature themes, even though these were being filtered through the simplistic lens of superheroes . Stacy's death would represent the end of the innocence of readers and of the lighter stories that had marked the period. [Italics are in the original].

An interesting fact is that, however creative an author/screenwriter may be, his intelligence and, consequently, his capacity for creation are subject to the advances and scientific discoveries of his time. Even if literature makes *poetic license*³ available to producers , this is limited by contemporary discoveries and evidence of what is intended to be written and presented to the public. Of course, endowed with infinite freedom (sic) to create, the authors fantasize many situations that, in real life, would prove impossible to occur. It should be noted that, without imagination and without the freedom to express what dominates and is produced in the world of the fantastic, no story would show enough brilliance to awaken pathos *in*⁴ the reader.

Even if it was silent and difficult to explain, the rules of Physics were always respected by authors [*even the most creative ones*] and, this in a very subjective, even unconscious way, even because the word Physics is a transliteration of *Physis*⁵, from Greek to Latin; thus, when

³Freedom granted to an artist, not necessarily a poet, to express himself creatively, without rigid obedience to a canon , a grammar , a code or a conventional model of writing . At the whim of this type of freedom, it is possible to find the most diverse deviations from the poetic norm , from false rhymes to verses with irregular meter , from obscene themes in times of moral restraint to the mixture of various forms of literary expression in the same composition. Given the natural difficulty in respecting all school rules, which obliged the poet to contain his creative imagination to programmed forms controlled by complex codes of poetics and rhetoric, poetic license often served to hide the impossibility of such rules being infallible and completely regulative of poetry. From the moment that modernism practically inaugurated the end of poetic arts and rhetorical codes, so that poetry could express itself with complete formal freedom, it becomes difficult to speak of poetic license, unless one uses a formula classical music, the sonnet, for example, without obeying its canonical rules. Today it is accepted that no form of literary expression can be subject to castrating rules of its artistic realization . (PERLOFF, Marjorie. *Poetic License: Essays on Modernist and Postmodernist Lyric* , 1990).

⁴ The word *pathos* comes from the Greek *pathos* (*πάθος*), with the meaning of deep feeling and, from the second century AD onwards, it came to mean suffering. From him came the term pathetic, used nowadays in a more pejorative than positive sense , signaling something excessively affected, such as melodrama.

⁵ *Physis* means dominant force (in force) of what sprouts and remains, in a constant sprouting and remaining and can be experienced everywhere, but it is not to be confused with the phenomena that today we call natural and gather in the expression nature. *Physis* should not be taken as any phenomenon, but as the being by virtue of which the entity becomes what it is and remains being, as long as its come-to-be lasts (becoming), making itself observable as such. As Martin Heidegger (1889-1976) affirms, when it was translated by Latin by *nature* , its original content was distorted and its evocative power was destroyed” (IBAIXE JÚNIOR, João. *Os pré-somáticos e a physis*).

one says that they respect Physics, one is not speaking, semantically, of science or school discipline; one is referring to brute and savage Nature, with its laws that cannot be changed by simple human interpellation or the whim of some writer or poet.

HG Wells (1866-1946) was a remarkably creative writer. To the point that his character creates a machine that allows him to travel through time, allowing him to go back to the past and try to save his bride from death. It fails every time it gets involved in the adventure. Wells knew [*or discovered, after his hero's failed experiments*] that it is possible for a human to prevent someone from being born; however, it is impossible to prevent someone from dying.

The death of Gwen Stacy allows the tragedy to be inserted in comics and, in the same way that the symbolism and editorial strategies used to give brightness and enhancement to the work, start to share space with the fateful, with what cannot be changed, because governed by a much more powerful force, even insurmountable. With this, the silent background of the stories becomes more scientific, *more human*, which some critics will interpret as *darker*.

It wasn't the way Gwen dies, with her neck broken, by Peter's blunder, that shocked fans into rage and some even sent death threatening letters to Marvel's newsroom. It was, quite simply, her death that generates this wave of hatred. His presence made the stories more charming, producing an air of lightness in the overall situation of the play. Without her, there would be a void that could never be filled.

Peter himself goes on with his life, not regretting his mistake..., because what he did was the most he could have done, in an attempt to save the life of the woman he loved. It was the fact of having lost someone else and that way he doesn't understand why tragedies and losses keep chasing him. For every human being, losses are interpreted, on an unconscious level, as abandonment! Somewhere in his mind, he wondered why Gwen had abandoned him..., a question that might seem ridiculous; but this is something human, all too human! And, Spider-Man is the most human of comic book Super Heroes!

Jason Sacks and Keith Dallas, in an essay published in 2019, tried, once again, without much prospect of being able to convince the public, to justify the decision to kill the wonderful Gwen in the comics. For them,

The relationship between Peter and Gwen has gone through many inconsequential ups and downs, and unless the two were married, there was nowhere else to take it. But, the marriage also felt wrong. Peter just wasn't ready. [*Not at that specific time* .] So Gerry, Roy and Stan debated the issue... They all came to the same inescapable conclusion. Gwen's death was simply destined to happen. Events shaped themselves in such a way that their only logical solution was tragedy. So don't blame Gerry. Don't blame Stan. Don't

blame anyone. Only the inscrutable and inexorable working of circumstances is to blame this time (SACKS and DALLAS, 2019, p. 37).

Gwen Stacy's death shocked the entire American comic book community. Before this epic event, it was unthinkable to kill off such an important character - the girlfriend of a protagonist with a huge fan base. Generally, a superhero doesn't fail so disastrously unless it's part of his origin story. This story arc was proposed as a marker of the beginning of the end of the Silver Age of Comics and the beginning of the Bronze Age, bringing darker stories and a strange feeling, which would come to be interpreted, already in the 21st Century, as the responsibility Social Applied to Superheroes. The subsequent tendency of male superhero wives and girlfriends to meet dark fates was dubbed the *Gwen Stacy Syndrome* by the Comic Book Buyer's Guide.

Stan Lee (1922-2018) has never forgiven himself for letting the writers kill off the star of the Friendly Neighborhood show. In an interview, in 2016, when asked about the episode, he was very direct: “ *I have nothing to do with this!*” There were other ways of deepening the anguish in Parker's life, creating conflicts *that were difficult* to overcome. For him, there was already the matter of the loss of his Uncle Ben, which was another real, fateful and non-symbolic tragedy [*although it could turn into a symbolic death at the hands of skilled surgeons*]; but, it wasn't and the guilt took over the boy, leading him to become a Super-Hero.

In a magical way, Ben Parker paved the way for social responsibility to be inserted in Super-Heroes comics. Its iconic phrase *With great power comes great responsibility* can be interpreted and understood as a prelude. In Peter's inability to interpret this oracular message from his Uncle, he is seized by anguish and melancholy to the point where, without the intervention of his creator, Norman Osborn and his Aunt May Parker, he would have left the mantle long ago. time.

CONCLUSION

Spider-Man is a superhero created in the midst of internal American conflicts generated by the famous and disastrous Vietnam War (1955-1975), in which a large movement within the North American country was already protesting against the continuation of the war and, in the midst of all of this, as the negative results in combat and the young, mutilated and insane soldiers , who returned home, made a wave of depression and uncertainty take over American teenagers and young people.

Peter Parker was the most perfect representation of this state of mind of the American population at that time; uncertain and insecure about the future and even more uncertain and insecure about the present. Bringing a figure as delicate and sweet as Gwen Stacy into his life was the right decision by the writers and editors, who served him as a true oasis in the middle of the desert that consumed him like a black hole.

Gwen's way of being, calm and serene, did not allow her to be placed in situations of despair as they did with Mary Jane, more haughty, more involved in life as a representative action, not least because she was a model and an extra in plays. She was used to performing well in front of an audience; therefore, she managed to move more during the risky situations in which she found herself involved.

Even if the writers had bolder plans for Peter in which Gwen did not fit them, Blonde's fateful [*and not symbolic*] death represents a disproportionate act against such an important character in comic book history. The story is classic and, despite all the criticisms that can be endorsed about it, it was very well constructed and presents a degree of perfection in the plot that is well reminiscent of a Greek tragic play.

Regarding the criticism of the Brazilian edition, in which the title already presents the conclusion of the play, it is enough to know that Eurípides (480-406 ane) was the one who introduced the prologue ⁶in the Greek theater, in which, before starting the presentation of the play, he made a summary of the main events and, even so, all the expectation was maintained with the same, because the interest was concentrated in the unfolding of the facts, in the plot as a whole.

As for the detail about Gwen's death, most Blondie or Neighborhood fans haven't forgiven the writers for what they did, not Gwen Stacy or Parker, but what they did to them. She deserves the place of honor that she holds in the memory of fans and, it can be said that over the next fifty years, several other works tend to emerge, enhancing her memory and her charming glow that, for years, guided Spider-Man through the dark path of being a teenage Super-Hero, with a load of enemies that would make any other of the genre, already established in the Comics World, envious.

All the longing that her fans show is a representation of an unconscious desire for an expectation that, one day, she will shine again in the stories of Arachnid. As has already been

⁶ **Prologue** is a **text or admonition** , usually brief, that precedes a written work and which aims **present it to the reader** . From the Greek *prologos* meaning *preliminary writing* . Prologue originally represented the opening part of a Greek drama, in which a single character performed, before the play itself.

explained in this essay, this could take a long time, because his departure from comics was fateful and not symbolic.

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